

ISic3542

Fragment of a Greek inscription

Language

Ancient Greek

Type**Material**

marble

Object

fragment

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Museo regionale interdisciplinare di Messina, inventory

A3632

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height 8 cm

Width 6 cm

Depth 3.1 cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1-2: 30 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not measured mm

Text

1. [---]IMH

2. [---]Υ,ΣΓΟ

3. [---]

Apparatus

Text from Bitto 2001

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 493879

EDCS 38200029

PHI 313677

Bibliography

Bitto, I. 2001. Le iscrizioni greche e latine di Messina. *Pelorias* 7. Messina. At 45

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